

TEACHING LISTENING SKILLS TO YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH MOVIES AND SONGS

S. Oganyan¹

(Scientific supervisor: Ashurova Nigina Alimdjanovna)

Abstract:

Listening skills play an important role in communication process. Regrettably, a substantial number of students and educators tend to overlook the significance of multimedia use in the process of learning and teaching. The subject of research in this article is the use of video and audio materials at a foreign language lesson. The article considers the usefulness of using multimedia with YL as a means of intensifying the learning process and giving it maximum communicative orientation. The methodology of working with multimedia and typology of exercises and tasks for each stage in teaching listening comprehension are proposed.

Key words: listening skills, young learners (YLs), types of listening, music, songs, movies.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/vethgh78>

Listening is the action of hearing words and sounds, making sense and evaluating them for meaning, and responding. Listening is a far more in-depth, conscious, and active process than hearing, which is the perception of words or sounds. Hearing a lawnmower sound as background noise is quite different than consciously listening to a friend's words for meaning and forming a meaningful response.

People listen in many contexts and environments, including education, employment, and social and personal relationships. The listening process is important for effective communication. Listening can help people learn better in a classroom or lecture environment and develop deeper relationships. Actively listening to what others are saying can convey that the person cares about others and is interested in their thoughts. The effort of listening can also result in a better understanding of others and perceived as curious and thoughtful.

Listening skills to young learners

Listening involves the receptive utilization of language, aiming to comprehend speech content. The primary emphasis lies in understanding the meaning conveyed rather than focusing solely on the language itself [2,240].

Two different theories regarding speech perception outline contrasting roles for listeners. In the first perspective, listeners are seen as passive participants, merely recognizing and decoding sounds. Conversely, the second perspective presents listeners as actively engaging in perceiving sounds by accessing internal articulation rules to decode speech [4,325]. Phillips argues that regardless of whether speech perception is active, passive, or a combination of both, listening tasks are vital in primary education as they offer a wealth of

¹Oganyan Stella Samvelovna, student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

language data for children to form their understanding of the foreign language. This understanding serves as a rich resource that young learners utilize in language production [7,99]. Listening serves as the foundational stage in both first and second language acquisition. Sharpe asserts that enhancing children's speaking and listening skills is crucial for effective learning across all subjects in the primary curriculum. Consequently, ESL/EFL teachers need to prioritize developing children's listening skills as a primary objective and equip them with effective listening strategies [9,150].

The Types of Listening for YLs students

- Comprehension listening the next step beyond discriminating between different sound and sights is to make sense of them. To comprehend the meaning requires first having a lexicon of words at our fingertips and also all rules of grammar and syntax by which we can understand what others are saying. The same is course, for the visual components of communication, and an understanding of body language helps us understand what the other person is really meaning. In communication, some words are more important and some less so, and comprehension often benefits from extraction of key facts and items from a long spiel. Comprehension listening is also known as content listening, informative listening and full listening.

- Critical listening when listeners have to evaluate a message and respond with their opinion, this is called critical listening. You need to scrutinize what is being said, and play an active role because it usually requires you to make a decision, form an opinion or solve a problem. Making a judgment requires you to assess the situation, and requires you to both listen to what's being said while analyzing it at the same time.

- Appreciative listening the final type of listening is listening for the sake of pure enjoyment. This includes music, theater, television, radio and films, where the ultimate response is the one from the listener (not the speaker).

- How to teach students through the songs

As language teachers, we should always bear in mind that our main responsibility is to teach the target language. No matter how fun and enjoyable song activities may be for YLs, we should not get carried away by the music and rhythm of songs. Our main responsibility is not to teach singing skills, but to teach the target language. Therefore, if songs are used ineffectively, they can easily become mere entertainment and pleasurable interruptions in the school day that, in the long term, result in boredom and a lack of interest. There should be a clear reason in the language teacher's mind as to why and how to use a song. Songs can be an effective means of developing children's language skills only when they are well integrated into a scheme of work and carefully selected for the cognitive and linguistic needs of pupils.

Kirsch states that listening activities should be based on meaningful, appropriate, and authentic texts (e.g., a story, song, or poem) that assist listening and remembering and that match the language and grade level of pupils [5,85].

According to Sharpe songs create a context for using real language in an enjoyable way. She asserts that singing is crucial for young children both in and out of school, and integrating a foreign language into this essential activity helps make it more familiar [9,155]. Young children tend to mimic sounds easily and often find joy in connecting singing and playing with rhythms and rhymes from an early age.[8] identifies three key patterns that research reveals about the value of songs in the ESL/EFL classroom

- Tips to Learn English Through Movies

According to Kusumaningrum Deny A.Maria in conducting an attractive classroom activities, teacher should be able to use suitable English movie [6]. Therefore, there are some points to consider during teaching and learning process, they are:

- find the genre that make you interested, choose a film with a storyline that tends to be light, so you can better digest the conversation in the film.

- use a subtitle, if you choose English movie, you need to use English subtitle. Because with that will know how to pronounce it clearly, to know how to write the word.

- Watching movies and listening skills

In this particular study, movie watching activity is refers to the activity of looking and paying attention to a movie. The watching activity here can be done by using any possible media, and with or without the aid of subtitle. The movie here refers to all genres of motion pictures that use English language in their narrative. However, the movies that have been dubbed to languages other than English are not included in the scope of this study. "Movies are typically used in English classes, but it can also be used in other fields, including Biology, Chemist, and History. In ESL and EFL classes, the use of movies also receives positive feedback from teachers. An experiment titled The Effectiveness of Using Movies in EFL Classroom shows that movies can develop students" listening and communication skills. Chan Deborah argues that visual literacy (the ability to interpret and create visual and audio media) is a fundamental form of literacy in the 21st century [3]. Training the speaking skill In speaking skill is for the adult or listener to be able to speak English accurately, fluently and contextually, the listeners should focus more on actress or actor' speaking activities during the movie go on. Training the writing skill by using English movies, also teach writing skill in a way the grammar, new vocabulary, use of articles, adverb placement, and adjective comparison.

Conclusion

Improving listening abilities is crucial programs for Young Learners (YLs), songs and movies are highly valued as a powerful method for this purpose. They hold a significant role in the YL classroom, offering engaging language practice that aids in enhancing listening skills. The aim is for YLs to become better language learners by experiencing a variety of songs which becomes more impactful.

Watching movies allows students to learn correct pronunciation and clear word articulation, while also gaining useful expressions. Through movies, they can acquire new vocabulary and grasp grammar concepts as well.

References:

[1]. Ashurova N. *The use of advertising texts in teaching a foreign language // Scope Academic House B&M Publishing.* – 2019. – C. 190.

[2]. Cameron L. *Teaching Languages to Young Learners.* Cambridge University Press; 2001. – 277 p.

[3]. Chan, Deborah, et al. *Using Film to Teach Languages.* 2018.- <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B07JDta9Ke4YLWFJX3RQUklJeFk/view>

[4]. Crystal D. *The Cambridge encyclopedia of language.* 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1997.- 488 p

[5]. Kirsch C. *Teaching foreign languages in the Primary School*. London. Continuum; 2008.-240 p.

[6]. Kusumaningrum Deny A. Maria. (2016). *Using English Movie as an Attractive Strategy to Teach Senior High School Students English as A Foreign Language*. *LLT Journal A Journal on Language and Language Teaching*; 2015.-
<https://doi.org/10.24071/llt.20>

[7]. Phillips S. *Young learners*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 1993.-188 p

[8]. Schoepp K. *Reasons for using songs in the ESL/EFL Classroom*. *The Internet TESL Journal*. 2001.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309390126_Reasons_for_Using_Songs_in_the_ESLEFL_Classroom

[9]. Sharpe, K. *Modern foreign languages in the primary school: The what, why and how of early MFL teaching*. London: Kogan Page; 2001.- 221 p.